

ETHICAL CONCERNS IN GENERATIVE AI

Saurav Sandesh

Department of Commerce and Management, B.R.A. Bihar University, Muzaffarpur, India
saurav.sandesh1981@gmail.com

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Abstract

Generative artificial intelligence (AI), known as Gen AI, has significantly impacted and is increasingly integrated into our lives. Gen AI represents a paradigm shift and a transformative leap in technology, enabling the creation of new content and solutions through advanced machine learning models. As AI has evolved, ethical concerns have become a relevant topic for discussion and debate in today's society. The objective of technology is to achieve better results and improve people's lives. No doubt, Gen AI can create new content like text, images, etc., form existing data and generate new output and has a wide area of applications such as content creation, art and design, scientific result, product development and so on. But, on the other hand, the ethical concerns of the Gen AI are complex, and it can be used for unethical and malicious purposes. It poses risks like deepfakes, cyberattacks and surveillance, ignoring the importance of ethical considerations. Ethical AI adheres to well-defined ethical guidelines, which include integrity, fairness, accountability, honesty and

environmental concerns. The ethical AI involves the fulfilment of basic human needs and the creation of credibility with the public. The purpose and guiding luminaries of Gen AI should be “निष्ठा, धृतिः, सत्यम्” (dedication, steadfastness and truth). In this context, the present paper is intended to define Generative AI and ethics; examine the features and risks related to Gen AI and lastly, suggest measures to make it useful for humanity. The scholar finds that Gen AI is here to stay in the world and let us reap the advantages for social well-being.

Keywords

Ethics, Generative AI, Technology, Environmental Concerns, Society.

INTRODUCTION

In a rapidly evolving digital content landscape, AI tools are revolutionising how we live and work. It enhances efficiency, automates tasks, improves decision making and can solve complex problems. The rapid advancement of generative artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, such as deep learning models, has

introduced significant ethical concerns that impact various sectors, including healthcare, finance, entertainment, and communication. Besides, the lack of transparency in how generative AI models operate complicates efforts to assign accountability for harmful content or decisions. Further, the increasing automation enabled by generative AI poses risks to employment, particularly in creative industries, where AI systems can produce human-like content, potentially displacing workers. AI chatbots are scarier than in Kubrick's movie. It is a far greater threat than climate disaster or nuclear war.¹ Addressing these concerns requires robust regulatory frameworks, transparency in AI development, and concerted efforts to make fairness, security, and answerability in the use of generative AI technologies. The present paper finds that AI presents both openings and ethical challenges and emphasises the need for ethical and transparent AI development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Various academic publications discuss ethical issues related to the ethical concerns in Gen AI. European Commission Report, the US, and China have formulated ethical guidelines for reliable and honest Gen AI. The guidelines by Jobin et.al., (2019) have also been acknowledged. "The Ethics of AI Ethics: An Evaluation of Guidelines" by Hagendroff (2020)² and Artificial Intelligence Ethics by Ryan and Carsten Stahi (2021) provide an elaborative analysis of AI ethical guidelines. Moreover, Morley et. al., (2020), Gerke et. al., (2020), Reddy et.al., and many more devoted their

studies to the concept of ethical concerns in AI. While Papernot et.al., (2017) advocate that generative models produce "data poisoning", Zheng et.al., (2021) emphasise that Gen AI can pose a direct threat to privacy. Again, Binns (2018)³ highlights the biases in Gen AI, and Vincent (2020) discusses the rising threat of deepfakes posing harm to societal trust. Though, there is no dearth of literature on artificial intelligence, yet the present study differs from above in the sense that it attempts to explore that there are some areas where it requires to clear the pathways to ethical considerations specific to Gen AI and offers an in depth analysis of the impacts of Gen AI across diverse public domains.

OBJECTIVES

1. To define the concepts of ethics and Generative AI and explore ethical concerns.
2. To evaluate the real-world implications of generative AI in terms of privacy, bias, misinformation, and its effects on the workforce.
3. To evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of Gen AI.
4. To propose solutions or guidelines to cope with issues pertaining to generative AI.
5. To suggest measures to relevant the potential of generative AI systems.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology adopted in the present article is qualitative, not quantitative; theoretical, not empirical; and suggestive, not experimental. The study is based on synthesizing academic papers, journals, newspapers, online available materials and other secondary sources, as well as ethical frameworks to interpret the current understanding of Gen AI and concerned ethical issues.

RESEARCH GAP

While there is plenty of research works and articles on artificial intelligence, the ethical considerations specific to generative AI remain underexplored in some areas. The ethical discourse around AI has often focused on general concerns such as transparency, bias, and decision-making algorithms. However, generative AI, due to its unique capabilities—such as content generation, imitation, and synthesis of data—presents additional ethical concerns that need distinct attention. This paper attempts to fill this gap by addressing the ethical issues arising from generative AI systems and offering an in-depth analysis of its implications across various domains.

ETHICS: DEFINITION

A set of principles placed by society on itself to guide the behaviour, choices and actions are known as ethics. It involves the concepts of right and wrong behaviour and is concerned with moral values. The term 'ethics' has a variety of meanings, such as "the principles of conduct governing an individual or a group".⁴ Ethics is what guides us, telling the truth, keeping our

promise and helping someone in need. Defining Ethics, Martinez (2019) states, "Ethics seek to resolve questions of human morality by defining concepts such as good and evil, right and wrong, virtue and vice, justice and crime."⁵ In other words, ethics refers to a system of moral principles, sense of righteousness, action and consequences. Ethics includes fairness, integrity, commitment, human respect and accountability (FICHA), shown in figure 1 below: -

Figure.1. FICHA- AN INDEX CARD

Ethics in Gen AI refers to the application of ethical principles to Gen AI situations. In the contemporary global landscape, where innovation of new ideas incorporating new technology is at an accelerating rate, an across-the-board effort is needed to fight deviation from ethical norms so far as the application of Gen AI is concerned.

GENERATIVE AI: DEFINITION

John Mc Carthy, known as the father of AI, defines AI as "the science and engineering of making intelligent machines, especially

intelligent computer programs.” A type of AI capable of creating new content on the basis of data it was trained on is called Gen AI. According to Long and Magerko (2020), “AI literacy refers to a set of competencies that enables individuals to critically evaluate AI technologies, communicate and collaborate effectively with AI.”⁶ Gen AI has revolutionised the way we operate. It helps in content personalisation, employee productivity and IT efficiency. It can learn human language, programming language and can create new content and ideas including stories, images, videos and music. It can reach a level of super intelligence beyond human comprehension. Besides, Gen AI can perform a lot of advisory work, i.e., travel, legal, financial, medical, etc. It removes drudgery in work and improves the ability to create data-based content. Examples of Gen AI tools are Chat GPT, Dall E-2, Midjourney, Sora and so on.

GENERATIVE AI: ADVANTAGES

In an era of technical excellence, Gen AI is becoming more and more important in data-centric fields. It offers many advantages:

To begin with, as Gen AI gathers pace, creativity is fuelling AI adoption across several areas. It is driving digital transformation across the board, and it has eliminated human interference, reduced work time frame and driven completeness and productivity.

Second, Gen AI is not just scalable and economical, but is the harbinger of a new

revolution. The seven pillars of cybersecurity- network, cloud, end point, mobile, IOT, application and zero trust— are creating an army of digital warriors.⁷

Third, Gen AI gets close to humans in intelligence and is set to surpass it. It can do assignments, write computer code, help plan a party, as well as suggest an itinerary. It can take away more complex and intelligent tasks. It can be used to create synthetic data to build more robust and trustworthy models. It holds enormous potential to create new capabilities and values.

Fourth, Gen AI also has advantages in industries. It improves operational efficiency, decision-making, and business outcomes. Machine learning has been used for various scientific and commercial purposes, including credit scoring and e-commerce. IT Services companies are strengthening generative AI offerings. P.B. Samuel, CEO, Everest Group, observes, “I believe that Gen AI will create a significant wave of work, perhaps adding as much as percentage points of growth to the industry.”

Fifth, Gen AI has grassroots reach. Through the AI-powered Bhashini application, citizens access to digital services in Indian languages has become possible. The PM-KISAN Scheme has an AI chatbot to assist and empower farmers in the country.

Sixth, Chat GPT is a useful tool that can generate coding. Grok, a chatbot developed by Elon Musk’s company xAI, has been developed “to understand

intuitively or by empathy, to establish rapport with.”

Finally, Gen AI boosts creativity, automation of tasks, enhanced business operations, faster research and development, and increased efficiency and innovation. Cole Porter AI rightly observes, “Birds do it, bees do it. Even educated fleas do it, Let's do it, let's chatbot.

GEN AI: DISADVANTAGES

Gen AI is developed and used in various ways. However, it bears some of the biggest risks. The disadvantages are: -

To begin with, Gen AI poses significant ethical challenges, bias, misinformation, and employment relegation. Any technology has little value if it cannot come up with ethical and creative ways and solve problems, drive better results and improve the lives of the people. Careful balancing between human and Gen AI is the essence of ethical Gen AI.

Second, the biggest worry with Gen AI is in the education sectors. It can keep students away from reading, analysing, critical thinking and researching. According to Dipankar Gupta, a sociologist, “AI can imitate authors and artists, but it is incapable of producing anything novel.”⁸

Third, a chatbot lacks the autonomy to make decisions or have a genuine impact on the world. AI chatbots sometimes use offensive language and produce “hallucinations”, including outright lies. Whatever improvements Gen AI models might have made, unless the algorithm and

training data are protected, it will continue to generate responses that will be contentious.

Fourth, biases still exist in one way or another in Gen AI applications. We cannot depend on AI when waging a war, planning for profit or plotting policies. Atanu Biswas states, “A Gen AI is more like a stochastic parrot imitating human language by matching statistical patterns.”

Lastly, a lack of transparency can lead to unintended consequences. In Gen AI, the line between human agency and machine decision-making becomes blurred. Similarly, Gen AI has been shown to produce “data poisoning” effects, where adversarial inputs lead to the creation of misleading outputs.⁹

EVALUATION AND FINDINGS

Generative AI has become the hottest sector in the contemporary environment of technical acceleration. But as the former British P.M. Asquith states, “totality of everything could be dangerous.” Human intelligence cannot be replaced by AI— AI can only be designed by human beings. No doubt, Gen AI provides immense opportunities to humanity, but its ethical implications are complex. The findings of this study are as follows: -

- I. Generative AI models have inherent biases. Although these models are undoubtedly quite good at prediction, they also train on low-quality content. Unless these are corrected, the expectation of offensive answers and

contentious responses cannot be denied.

- II. Whatever improvements AI models might have made, they lack any human-like sense of what is 'true or false.'
- III. Data is actually the lifeblood of Gen AI. But aside from quality data sources, there is occasionally the possibility of low-quality content. Determining the quality of the data churning algorithm is really challenging. Churning for nectar might produce kalkut, the toxin that kills.¹⁰
- IV. Generative AI models contribute to the spread of misinformation, deepfakes, and social inequality and pose ethical challenges.
- V. There is a need for transparent AI models for creating systems that are fair, accountable and salutary to society as a whole.

CONCLUSION

Despite extensive prospects to create new talent and value, Gen AI has also introduced new risks and challenges – legal, financial, reputational, and, above all, ethical. There is a need to evolve the twin objectives of using technology with sensitivity and ensuring the safety and security of the global people. Technology is nothing. What is important is the faith in human intelligence to perform wonders in this tech-centric digital wonderland. Gen AI and Ethics may appear to be poles asunder, but they can be welded into a scrupulous unit for the betterment of society as a whole. What we need today is not the

change of the system but change in our attitude and the cleansing of the heart—
“आ नो भद्राः क्रतवो यन्तु विश्वतः” (let noble thoughts come to us from all directions).

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